

Sclerocarya birrea

Marula

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 18 m tall.

Distribution:

The species is native to large parts of sub-Saharan Africa (including, but not limited to South Africa, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe). In South Africa, it is found in Limpopo, Mpumalanga, KwaZulu Natal, North West and some parts of Northern and Eastern Cape.

Importance:

Sclerocarya birrea is an economically and culturally important African tree, valued for products such as Amarula Cream Liqueur, cosmetic oil, and its traditional medicinal uses, while also supporting rural livelihoods. Its drought tolerant and deep rooting system make it important in agroforestry and ecosystem resilience. Sequencing its genome will improve understanding of its biology, support conservation and breeding efforts, and enhance sustainable commercial development.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 86.86 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 17.18 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.39 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.8% [Single: 97.4%, Duplicated: 1.4%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 22 676.94 kilobases
Contig number: 1 650

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